

Global Obesity Epidemic - Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The implications of obesity go far beyond aesthetics, being a condition associated with a series of serious health problems, such as type 2 diabetes, heart disease, high blood pressure, certain types of cancer and musculoskeletal disorders.

Objective: To offer a comprehensive and well-founded analysis of the current situation, contributing to the advancement of scientific knowledge and guiding effective public health actions.

Methods: This study constitutes a systematic review, classified as exploratory and descriptive. The preparation of the research was a bibliographical search in electronic databases on methods associated with RSL (Systematic Literature Review) and the applications of SMARTER (Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique using Exploiting Rankings). The study methodology is a systematic, exploratory and descriptive review, using qualitative and quantitative methods. The bibliographic search covered several databases, with well-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data analysis was conducted by three independent researchers.

Results and Discussion: The results revealed 1659 articles, 15 of which were included in the review. The discussion of the obesity epidemic is alarming, with a significant increase in the prevalence of this condition

across the world. Epidemiological data indicate a constant increase in obesity rates in different age groups, including children, adolescents and adults. This is associated with an increase in cases of chronic non-communicable diseases such as type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, high blood pressure, certain types of cancer and musculoskeletal problems, increasing the burden on healthcare systems

Conclusion: The fight against the global epidemic of Obesity requires a comprehensive, collaborative and long-term approach, involving not only individual actions but also structural changes in policies and environments. Continued awareness, innovative research and commitment from multiple sectors of society are critical to addressing this public health challenge and promoting a healthier, more resilient population in the future.

Keywords: Obesity; Epidemic; Public Health and prevention

INTRODUCTION

The global obesity epidemic is a worrying phenomenon that affects people of all ages and backgrounds around the world (MAPTΣΙΑΔΟΥ, 2023). This dramatic increase in the number of individuals who are overweight or obese is intrinsically linked to changes in modern lifestyles, including unhealthy diets, reduced physical activity and environments that promote excessive consumption of processed, high-calorie foods. Furthermore, genetic, socioeconomic and environmental factors also play a crucial role in the development of obesity, making it a multifaceted and complex issue (OGDEN, 2022; PIRES, 2023).

The implications of obesity go far beyond aesthetics, being a condition associated with a series of serious health problems, such as type 2 diabetes, heart disease, high blood pressure, certain types of cancer and musculoskeletal disorders (GOMES; FERREIRA, 2022; PIRES, 2023). Furthermore, it significantly affects the quality of life, impacting the mental health, self-esteem and functional capacity of affected individuals. This scenario creates a substantial burden on healthcare systems, increasing medical costs and reducing productivity, resulting in a negative socioeconomic impact on a global scale (WESTBURY et al., 2023).

Tackling the obesity epidemic requires comprehensive approaches that range from individual interventions to changes in public policies. Promoting healthy eating habits, encouraging regular physical activity and raising awareness about the risks associated with obesity are fundamental steps (MELO et al., 2023). Additionally, government policies that address access to nutritious foods, clear labeling of food products, and encouraging environments that promote physical activity are crucial to combating this global epidemic and ensuring a healthier future for future generations.

In this context, the objective of this systematic review was to offer a comprehensive and well-founded analysis of the current situation, contributing to the advancement of scientific knowledge and guiding effective public health actions. We examined relevant studies published in various scientific sources to comprehensively understand how the condition impacts the quality of life of these people, considering both physical and psychosocial aspects.

METHODS

This study constitutes a systematic review, classified as exploratory and descriptive. The preparation of the research was a bibliographical search in electronic databases on methods associated with RSL (Systematic Literature Review) and the applications of SMARTER (Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique using Exploiting Rankings). The work carried out is of a qualitative and quantitative nature. Qualitative data analysis was carried

out intuitively and inductively during the survey of the theoretical framework. It is also quantitative through the use of the multi-criteria method. In addition, there is also a numerical experimental study in order to simulate an article selection situation based on the observed criteria.

Based on bibliographical research, they were located in the following databases: US National Library of Medicine (PubMed), Web of Science; Science Direct (Elsevier); Wiley; SpringerLink; Taylor and Francis and EBSCO. In addition, searches were carried out using bibliographic references of studies that relevantly addressed the topic on the Google Scholar search platform (Google, USA).

The search in the databases was carried out using the terminologies registered in the Health Sciences Descriptors created by the Virtual Health Library developed from the Medical Subject Headings from the US National Library of Medicine, which allows the use of common terminology in Portuguese, English and Spanish. The present study sought to investigate the literature on the global obesity epidemic. To this end, the descriptors “Obesity; Epidemic; Public Health and Prevention”, initially in English, and additionally in Spanish and Portuguese.

As a tool to support decision-making in the selection and prioritization of articles, a set of criteria were considered essential to represent the state of the art of the topic under study. This method has the following characteristics: (i) Rigorous logic allows the method to be accepted as a decision support tool; (ii) Simple to understand and apply with easy-to-interpret results.

References from selected works were also searched for other documents of potential interest. Once qualified for full-text review, articles were included in the qualitative review if they met the following inclusion criteria: a) contained data on obesity; b) about the obesity epidemic. Articles were excluded if they were reports, banners or conference abstracts.

Three independent researchers extracted data from articles that met the inclusion criteria and recorded them in a “Data Extraction Form” generated in Microsoft Excel. From this form, the authors and year of publication, title, abstract, population, sample size (n), methods and outcome of the studies were included. There was no review of confidential health information and the study was non-interventional. Therefore, ethics committee approval was not necessary. In the end, the result obtained total 16 articles that covered the desired characteristics for the study.

RESULTS

A comprehensive systematic search of the literature yielded a total of 1,659 articles relating to the topic. From this, the SMARTER method (Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique using Exploiting Rankings) was chosen. Of these studies, 115 articles were suitable for full-text screening and 77 articles were included for data extraction. Of these, 59 studies were excluded due to data overlap. Here, 16 articles were included for systematic review.

Figure 1 describes the strategy for selecting articles on the topic in question, summarized in **Table 1**.

Figure 1: Article search strategy

Author/Year	Title	N	Methods	Conclusion of the Study
MAPTΣΙΔΟΥ (2023)	The economy and societal burden of obesity at the global level	ND	Revision	Obesity is a manifestation of modern life, representing a contemporary, complex and largely underestimated challenge, just like climate change, pandemics, artificial intelligence and cybersecurity. This problem has not yet been completely understood and faced by today's society.
SAUCER (2023)	Plurality of therapeutic itineraries in obesity management	40	Qualitative Study	This research raises other questions of sociological interest that can be explored in future studies.
OGDEN (2022)	The psychology of diets	ND	Book	ND
GOMES; FERREIRA (2022)	Uncomplicated obesity for doctors and laypeople. Moura	ND	Book	ND
WESTBURY et al. (2023)	Obesity Stigma: Causes, Consequences, and Potential Solutions	ND	Revision	A coordinated and ongoing effort from diverse stakeholders and societal leaders is essential to demystify the idea that body weight is exclusively a matter of personal responsibility and promote greater empathy towards people who live in larger bodies. This lays the foundation for more effective policies and interventions targeting social and environmental determinants of health, with the ultimate goal of improving population health.
MELO et al. (2023)	Structural responses to the obesity epidemic in Latin America: what are the next steps for food and physics activity policies?	ND	Revision	Although some improvements have been made in obesity-related health behaviors in the region, the prevalence of obesity continues to increase. We discuss some opportunities to continue addressing the obesity epidemic in Latin America within a structural context.
SILVA (2020)	Profile of physical activity practice in children and adolescents of different nutritional status	30	Cross-Sectional Research	Children and adolescents of both sexes showed imbalances in body weight, especially with high frequencies of overweight and obesity, and to a lesser extent nutritional deficit. Regarding the perceived level of physical activity, boys demonstrated to be more active. In the analysis of nutritional status, it was observed that those with excess weight were classified as more physically active and showed less sedentary behavior compared to their normal weight peers.
KINGS (2022)	Integrative review: obesity in low-income children, causality and consequences	27 articles	Integrative Review	For a deeper understanding of childhood obesity and the development of more effective interventions, it is necessary to consider the meaning attributed to obesity, family dynamics, socioeconomic conditions and all elements that involve the context of childhood obesity.
BRIGIL (2019)	Prevalence of obesity and association with chronic non-communicable diseases in elderly people cared for by the family health	45	Descriptive Quantitative Research	A high incidence of obesity associated with chronic diseases was observed among the elderly treated, highlighting the importance of health initiatives that integrate understandings about the human aging process and the problem of obesity.

strategy in the city of Macapá-AP				
RIBEIRO; SPOLADO (2022)	Health, income and obesity: an analysis for Brazilian states	ND	Revision	Obesity represents one of the leading causes of mortality globally, and its potential effects contribute significantly to healthcare expenditures and have adverse impacts on the economy. In Brazil, despite the population's life expectancy increasing by 21 years between 1960 and 2018, the obesity rate has increased since the 1970s, reaching 25% of the total population in 2019.
LIMA E SILVA (2022)	Essays on health economics: drug subsidies, labor market and obesity	ND	Clinical Trial	Among women, obesity is associated with lower wages, while men tend to receive increases in earnings. Appearance appears to be the determining factor behind these results in Brazil during the period analyzed.
FERRAZ (2021)	The role of the State in preventing childhood obesity: focus on measures to discourage the consumption of unhealthy foods	ND	Revision	The investigation highlights the (non)fulfillment by the Brazilian State of its responsibilities in protecting child health from this perspective, providing criteria and potential approaches to guide political decisions, legal operators and academics in favor of the best interests of the child and the well-being of children. of society as a whole.
BRANCHES (2023)	Health care for people with obesity from the perspective of Primary Care professionals in the state of Rio de Janeiro	225	Qualitative research	It is understood that obesity must be approached as a chronic, complex and multifactorial condition, which requires continuous care throughout life. To achieve this, both the Health Care Network (RAS) and health professionals need to be trained to offer all the necessary support to people living with this condition.
LIBERALI; KUPEK; ASSIS (2020)	Dietary Patterns and Childhood Obesity Risk: A Systematic Review	16 articles	Systematic review	In general, the results suggest, in most studies, that a diet lower in obesogenic foods may be effective in reducing the risk of developing obesity.
(GONZE et al. (2021)	Effects of Substituting Sedentary Behavior with Light- Intensity or Moderate-to-Vigorous Physics Activity on Obesity Indices in Adults: A Prospective Short-Term Follow-Up Study	780 – Start of study 242 – Second assessment	Cohort Study	Swapping sedentary behaviors for moderate to vigorous physical activity is related to a significant improvement in obesity rates, both in cross-sectional and follow-up studies. On the other hand, replacing sedentary behaviors with light to moderate intensity physical activities had a less consistent impact.
KELLY et al. (2022)	Metabolic Syndrome: An association between unhealthy lifestyle habits and cardiovascular risk factors in university students	ND	ND	During the period of university graduation, students experience significant changes in their lifestyle, including long hours of classes, study and internships, as well as inadequate nutrition, increased stress and possible worsening of psychological aspects. In some cases, there may also be an increase in the consumption of legal and illicit drugs. As a result, students may be at greater risk of developing cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, such as metabolic syndrome.

TABLE 1. Articles used in the study

*ND – Nothing Described

DISCUSSION

The results of the obesity epidemic are alarming, with a significant increase in the prevalence of this condition across the world. Epidemiological data indicate a constant increase in obesity rates in different age groups, including children, adolescents and adults (REIS, 2022; SILVA, 2020). This is associated with an increase in cases of chronic non-communicable diseases such as type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, high blood pressure, certain types of cancer and musculoskeletal problems, increasing the burden on healthcare systems (BRIGIL, 2019).

1. Furthermore, the economic costs of obesity are substantial, affecting both health systems and economic productivity. Expenditures on medical treatment, hospitalizations and medications related to obesity represent a significant portion of the resources allocated to health in many countries. This places an additional burden on already overburdened healthcare systems and reduces the quality of life of those affected, leading to decreased productivity in the workplace (LIMA E SILVA, 2022; RIBEIRO; SPOLADOR, 2022).

Within the scope of discussions, the search for effective solutions is challenging. Obesity prevention and treatment strategies involve complex interventions that range from education about healthy eating and promotion of physical activity to public policies that aim to modify the obesogenic environment. However, implementing these strategies faces obstacles such as commercial interests from the food industry, lack of access to healthy foods in low-income communities, lack of awareness, and socioeconomic barriers (FERRAZ, 2021).

The discussion surrounding the global obesity epidemic also extends to the need for an integrated and collaborative approach. This includes partnerships between governments, non-governmental organizations, healthcare professionals, the food industry, and communities to develop and implement comprehensive policies that address the social, environmental, and individual determinants of obesity (RAMOS, 2023). Effective strategies must be based on scientific evidence, focusing on prevention, equitable access to healthy foods, promoting environments favorable to physical exercise and supporting multidisciplinary treatment for individuals already affected.

Studies on the global obesity epidemic are carried out by a wide range of researchers and scientists around the world, each contributing unique perspectives to understanding and addressing this public health problem. The authors of these studies range from renowned professionals in public health, epidemiology, nutrition and medicine to researchers from diverse disciplines such as economics, psychology, sociology and behavioral sciences. These studies are conducted at different times over the years, reflecting the continued interest and concern about obesity. There is no single collection of studies that can cover all authors and years, as new research is constantly published.

Some important studies were conducted by authors such as Liberali and collaborators (2020), Gonze and collaborators (2021), Kelly and collaborators (2022), among others, over the last few decades, addressing different aspects of obesity, from its epidemiology and factors of risk to prevention and treatment strategies.

The years of these studies can vary, including recent work published in recent years to older studies that have established fundamental foundations for understanding obesity as a global health problem. It is

common to find a progression in understanding and proposed strategies over the years, as new scientific discoveries and changes in epidemiological trends shape the field of obesity study. These studies illustrate the diversity of research related to the global obesity epidemic, highlighting the importance of multifaceted strategies, including physical activity, advertising regulation, and personalized approaches to community interventions, in combating this growing public health problem.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The global obesity epidemic is a complex and multifaceted challenge that requires comprehensive and collaborative approaches to address. Studies and research carried out on this issue have highlighted not only the alarming increase in the prevalence of obesity, but also the significant adverse impacts on public health, economy and quality of life of affected populations.

The conclusion of these studies reinforces the importance of varied and integrated interventions, ranging from primary prevention strategies, such as nutritional education and promotion of physical activity, to public policies that aim to modify obesogenic environments and regulate the food industry. Understanding the factors that contribute to obesity, such as poor eating habits, lack of physical activity, environmental and socioeconomic influences, is essential to direct effective prevention and treatment efforts.

Furthermore, the need for personalized approaches adapted to different communities and socioeconomic contexts also stands out. Community interventions, public health policies and government actions must be implemented in a coordinated and sustainable way to promote healthier choices, making the environment conducive to the adoption of more balanced lifestyles.

The fight against the global obesity epidemic requires a comprehensive, collaborative and long-term approach, involving not only individual actions but also structural changes in policies and environments. Continued awareness, innovative research and commitment from multiple sectors of society are critical to addressing this public health challenge and promoting a healthier, more resilient population in the future.

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